

Studies on binary metal chelates. Part-III. Binary metal chelates of lanthanides(III) with coordinated amino acids

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Manuscript received 13 October 1998, revised 22 March 1999, accepted 23 April 1999

The proton-ligand association constant ($\log K_H$) of *trans*-[Co(en)₂Cl.glyH]²⁺ and *trans*-[Co(en)₂Cl.β-alaH]²⁺ and the stability constants of mixed metal binuclear complexes of *trans*-[Co(en)₂Cl.glyH]²⁺ and *trans*-[Co(en)₂Cl.β-alaH]²⁺ with trivalent lanthanide ions have been evaluated. The proton and metal ion binding site is the unbound primary amine group of cobalt(III) substrate. Thermodynamic parameters of the complexation reaction are also presented.

Studies on the formation of binary and ternary complexes between coordinated amino acids and metal ions are important to understand the role of metalloenzymes and metalloproteins¹. We reported earlier the formation of various binuclear complexes with coordinated amino acids². We now report the formation constants of coordinated amino acids with trivalent lanthanide ions. Thermodynamic parameters have also been calculated in order to evaluate the effect of temperature on the formation constants.

Results and Discussion

From the pH-titration data, values of the acidity constants of *trans*-[Co(en)₂Cl.glyH]²⁺ and *trans*-[Co(en)₂Cl.β-alaH]²⁺ were obtained by the method of Irving and Rossotti³. The acid dissociation of the N-protonated glycinate and β-alaninato complexes are given by equations (1) and (2) respectively,

The values of \bar{n}_A (average number of protons bound per Co^{III} complex by the amino function) were evaluated³ at various pH values from the titration curves for complex + HNO₃, and HNO₃ alone. The stability constants of the binuclear complexes, *trans*-[Co(en)₂Cl.glyM]⁴⁺ and *trans*-[Co(en)₂Cl.β-alaM]⁴⁺ (M(III) = La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Sm, Gd, Tb, Dy and Yb) at different temperatures (Table 1) were calculated with the help of the formation curves (\bar{n} vs pL, where L denotes the Co^{III} complex and \bar{n} the average number of L bound per M(III) ion). The values of \bar{n} and the ex-

Table 1. Proton-ligand stability constant ($\log K_H$) of the complexes and formation constants ($\log K$) of the binuclear complexes of Ln(III)

Metal ion	10 ²⁹ charge radii C m ⁻¹	Chloroglycinate					Chloro-β-alaninate				
		log K			ΔH	ΔS	log K			ΔH	ΔS
		298 K	303 K	318 K	kJ mol ⁻¹	JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	298 K	303 K	318 K	kJ mol ⁻¹	JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
H ⁺		6.02	6.04	6.08	4.19	129.6	6.06	6.09	6.15	6.31	137.5
La ^{III}	4.10	4.19	4.29	4.40	14.92	131.2	4.00	4.06	4.15	10.74	113.2
Ce ^{III}	4.17	4.36	4.44	4.51	10.59	119.7	4.16	4.25	4.35	13.50	125.8
Pr ^{III}	4.25	4.41	4.50	4.64	16.48	140.6	4.22	4.30	4.40	12.83	124.6
Nd ^{III}	4.28	4.58	4.67	4.77	13.50	133.8	4.36	4.44	4.53	12.08	124.8
Sm ^{III}	4.36	4.80	4.89	4.98	12.76	135.6	4.51	4.59	4.73	16.33	141.9
Gd ^{III}	4.44	4.95	5.04	5.11	11.26	133.4	4.69	4.78	4.88	13.50	135.9
Tb ^{III}	4.53	5.02	5.10	5.17	10.59	132.4	4.80	4.88	4.94	9.85	125.6
Dy ^{III}	4.57	5.10	5.18	5.27	12.08	138.9	4.92	4.99	5.08	11.41	133.2
Yb ^{III}	4.75	5.51	5.62	5.71	14.10	153.8	5.32	5.41	5.52	14.25	150.5

ponent pL for the uncomplexed cobalt(III) substrates were calculated from the titration curve for cobalt(III) substrate in the presence of M(III) ions using the formula of Irving and Rossotti⁴. The values of the overall change in enthalpy (ΔH°) for the complexation equilibria were calculated using Van't Hoff equation and the ΔS° values using Gibbs equation, $\Delta G^\circ = \Delta H^\circ - T\Delta S^\circ$. It is worth noting that the stability of the 1 : 1 binuclear species of M(III) with *trans*-[Co(en)₂Cl.gly]⁺ and *trans*-[Co(en)₂Cl.β-ala]⁺ follow the order : La^{III} < Ce^{III} < Pr^{III} < Nd^{III} < Sm^{III} < Gd^{III} < Tb^{III} < Dy^{III} < Yb^{III}. Issa and Hegazy⁵ reported the formation constants of trivalent Sc, Y, La, Ce, Pr, Sm, Eu, Gd, Tb, Dy, Ho, Yb with some acid azo dyes. Nagar *et al.*⁶ reported the formation constants of some trivalent lanthanides, viz. La^{III}, Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, Gd^{III} and Dy^{III} with oxydiacetic acid (ODA), tartaric acid (TRA), malic acid (MEA), iminodiacetic acid (IDA) and glycine (GLY) as ligands. In both of these studies almost same order has been reported. The stability constant order of binary complexes are found to be in accordance with the increasing ionic potential of the metal ions (Table 1). The periodicity in $\log K$ (i.e. formation constant in general) values has been examined by $\log K$ vs $4f^q$ (q is the number of $4f$ electrons in Ln(III) ions) (Fig. 1). The proton-ligand association constant $\log K_H$ increases from 6.02 to 6.08 for the chloroglycinato complex and 6.06 to 6.15 for the chloro-β-alaninato complex when temperature was changed from 298 to 318 K. The K_H values of chloro-β-alaninato complex are found to be greater than that of the chloroglycinato complex. This is also expected, because in chloro-β-alaninato complex shifting of NH₂ group to beta-carbon makes these protonated amine less acidic than that of the chloroglycinato complex where the NH₂ group is attached to the alpha-carbon atom. This may be perfectly due to the favourable electrostatic repulsion effect of the proto-

nated amine and cobalt(III) centre for glycinato complex.

The formation constant values further reflect that the complexing ability of the half-bonded glycine in *trans*-[Co(en)₂Cl.gly]⁺ is higher than that of β-alanine in *trans*-[Co(en)₂Cl.β-ala]⁺ as observed in the corresponding mononuclear metal-ligand chelate complexes due to ring size effect. The glycinato complex forms a five-membered chelate ring with the metal ions, whereas β-alaninato complex forms six-membered chelate ring. It is known that five-membered chelate ring is less strained than six-membered chelate ring, therefore the former is more stable than the latter.

The fact that the stability sequence of these binuclear species is opposite to that of the K_H of the corresponding Co^{III} substrates, suggests that the binuclear species have chelate structure involving the amino group and carboxylate group already bound to the cobalt(III) centre.

Experimental

trans-[Co(en)₂Cl.glyH]²⁺ and *trans*-[Co(en)₂Cl.β-alaH]²⁺ were prepared by reported method⁷. Ln(III) nitrate (99.99% purity) were supplied by the Indian Rare Earths Limited. Other chemical were of A.R. grade. The solutions were prepared in double-distilled water. The Ln(III) solutions were standardized by complexometric titrations⁸.

Three mixtures of the following composition were prepared : (a) blank (0.004 M HNO₃ and 0.1 M NaNO₃), (b) blank + 0.003 M Co^{III} complex and (c) blank + 0.003 M Co^{III} complex + 0.001 M Ln³⁺. The mixtures were titrated pH-metrically against 0.1 mol dm⁻³ NaOH. Potentiometric measurement was made by a Toshniwal CI-46 pH meter with a glass-silver chloride combination electrode.

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Fig. 1. Plots of $\log K$ vs $4f^q$ (where q stands for number of $4f$ electrons) : (A) glycinato complex and (B) β-alaninato complex.